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Workpackage 4

Responsible Partner: ANSES (FR)

Contributing partners: SVA (SE)

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BIOPIGEE

Model Output: Number of animal cases with and without biosecurity measures

Participating countries

FR (ANSES), SE (SVA)

Background

Spread and maintenance of swine pathogens are the result of complex epidemiological processes leading to chains of contact connecting susceptible to infectious hosts. Hepatitis E virus (HEV) transmission occurs within-farm through direct and environmental faecal-oral routes. Because of its potential of moving infected animals from farm to farm, live animal trade is a major driver of between farms spread for infectious diseases of livestock such as hepatitis E.

Objective

In this study, we aim to simulate realistic between-farm movements to feed a multilevel epidemiological model. The objective was to quantify the impact of biosecurity measures on HEV transmission.

Methods

Swine movements from 2017 to 2019 in France provided by the National Swine Identification database (BDporc) were analysed using complex network analysis (CNA) methods. Exponential random graph models were then used to identify the key drivers of trade partner choices and the associated probabilities of contact between farms. Based on those, networks with similar characteristics were simulated and imported into SimInf Modelling framework to represent the spread of hepatitis E virus among the swine production chain, accounting for the prevalence of immunomodulating co-infections, known as favoring HEV transmission. Finally, transmission parameters were tuned to represent the impact of different biosecurity protocols on the spread of the virus.

Results

The baseline scenario, with transmission parameters derived from the literature and experiments, yield prevalences reaching 5.5% of slaughter age pigs (range 5 – 5.8%). The first biosecurity measure represented in the model relied on the reduction of the environmental viral pool considering faeces

removal rate through slatted floor. However, removing up to 80% of infectious material only led to a reduction of the prevalence of pigs with HEV at slaughter age down to 4.7% (4.5 – 5%). Similarly, cleaning and disinfection protocols during the empty period between batches was not found to impact the transmission dynamics with prevalence remaining in the same magnitude. Concerning HEV, the only control measure that was found to significantly modify the transmission dynamics relied on the reduction of the prevalence of co-infected herds. Indeed, reducing the percentage of herds infected with an immunomodulatory virus down to 50% would limit the prevalence of HEV positive pigs at slaughter down to 2.2% (2 – 2.6%).

Conclusion

HEV is a zoonosis for which pig liver products represent a risk for public health. Our results show that considering control measures targeting HEV alone in pig farms could be a mistake for different reasons. The first one relies on the absence of clinical expression in pigs, impairing direct diagnosis on farms. Then, the virus is known to be highly resistant in the environment, requiring huge cleaning and disinfection effort for virus elimination. Finally, the interplay between HEV and immunomodulatory viruses, as PRRSV or PCV2, had been documented as a pivotal factor regarding the transmission of the virus. Therefore, the HEV issue has to be taken as a whole, accounting for all factors affecting the transmission process. In this study, the role of co-infecting immunomodulatory viruses was again underlined, opening up on two possible ways to limit the risk for human health: reducing the burden of co-infecting viruses (and, in consequence, HEV prevalence); focusing the production of at-risk products in regions free from immunomodulating viruses at least PRRSV).

Future work

To better handle the role of immunomodulatory viruses on the transmission dynamics a model coupling the spread of the two viruses on farms would be required. That way, increasing biosecurity procedures on farms would certainly affect the spread of the co-infecting virus which, in turn, would modify the spread of HEV.

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